

Detection of phishing websites using Machine Learning Techniques

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Abstract— With the developing interaction of the Internet and public activity, the Internet is taking a gander at how individuals learn and work, however it likewise opens us to raising genuine security dangers. Step by step instructions to perceive different system assaults, especially attacks not seen already, is a key issue that should be unraveled critically. The target of phishing website URLs is to gather the individual data like client's name, passwords and on the web banking exchanges. Phishers use the sites which are outwardly and semantically like those of genuine sites. Since a large portion of the clients go online to get to the administrations given by government and financial foundations, there has been a significant increment in phishing assaults in last few years. Machine learning is a useful asset used to endeavor against phishing assaults. There are a few strategies or ways to deal with identifying phishing sites. The fundamental point of this paper is to execute the framework with high efficiency, exactness and cost effectively. The task is actualized utilizing 4 ML managed classification models. The four classification models are K-Nearest Neighbor, Kernel Support vector machine, Decision tree and Random Forest classifier. It was discovered that the Random Forest classifier is most accurate for the chosen dataset and gives an accuracy score of 96.82%.

Keywords- Machine Learning, classification, Cyber security, Phishing, KNN, Kernel SVM, Decision Tree, Random Forest Classifier

I. INTRODUCTION

As innovation keeps on developing, phishing strategies began to advance quickly and this should be forestalled by utilizing against phishing systems to distinguish phishing. Several anti-phishing tools are available and has its own disadvantages. The paper concentrates on basic Machine learning supervised classification techniques to find a solution to phishing attacks.

Supervised classification involves labeled dataset that is used to train the model. All the four algorithms used, namely; K- Nearest Neighbor, Kernel support vector machine, decision tree and random forest classifier are classification models. The dataset chosen has thirty features that are considered to classify a website as phishing or legitimate.

II. RELATED WORK

This section concentrates on the previous works carried out to detect phishing websites using Machine learning.

A phishing detection model which is based on a method that involves optimal features' selection and also neural network was proposed [1]. This work involves, feature validity value, a new index that is generated to check the impact of the features on detection of phishing websites. Then based on this index an algorithm is created to get the optimal features from phishing websites.

Fuzzy Rough Set hypothesis [2] is executed as a technique to find the most impactful features from a few standard datasets. The features that are selected are then fed to classifiers for detection of phishing.

A three-phase phishing attack detection model [3] called as Web Crawler based Phishing Attack Detector was proposed. It takes as input features the web content, traffic and URL. Based on those features, phishing or non-phishing website classification is made.

A detection system was proposed [4] that matches the dynamic environment with the phishing websites. This is absolutely a client-side arrangement and doesn't require any third-party help.

Parse Tree validation is another technique that is proposed to detect phishing website [5]. The approach makes use of hyperlinks of current page by utilizing the Google API and builds a parse tree with intercepted hyperlinks. The parsing starts from the root and follows the Depth first search algorithm and checks if any intermediate or leaf nodes has the value same as the root.

Feature engineering plays a vital role in detection of phishing websites although, accuracy depends a lot on the knowledge of features. To extract features from different dimensions are very useful but also time consuming. To fix this drawback, a multidimensional feature [6] detection of phishing was proposed which is a fast method.

A method which combines the collection, validation and detection of phishing websites into a tool online was proposed. It monitors the PhishTank's blacklist [7] and detects websites that are phishing in real time.

A solid relationship was worked between the identified heuristics and the authenticity of a site by dissecting training sets of sites (both phishing and authentic sites) and in the system break down new patterns and report findings. A system called Phishing-Detective [8] is introduced that distinguishes phishing sites dependent on existing and recently discovered heuristics.

Among a few phishing discoveries schemes, the plan utilizing visual closeness is gathering looks. It takes a screen capture of site and stores it to a database. In the event that the info site's screen capture is practically like the database's one, it is anticipated as phishing. In any case, if numerous comparative sites exist, the first input site is viewed as genuine. Therefore, it can't effectively foresee real site and perceiving phishing objective becomes troublesome. Visual similarity based phishing detection strategy [9] is proposed utilizing picture and CSS with target site finder.

III. PROPOSED SYSTEM

The architecture of the proposed system is as shown in figure 3.1. The URLs that are to be distinguished as either phishing or legitimate is the input to the classifier. The dataset is split into training and testing dataset. The training part of the dataset is utilized to train the classifier. The classifier recognizes the pattern from the training dataset. To test for the classifier, the testing part of the dataset is used. The classifier then predicts any URL as either phishing or legitimate based on the pattern learnt.

Fig: 3.1 System architecture

To give a detailed view of the system, figure 3.2 gives a level 2 data flow diagram in Gane-Sarson notation.

Fig: 3.2. level 2 DFD of the system

The above figure shows the system being categorized into three as preprocessing, feature scaling and classification. The details are graphically depicted and gives an idea of how the system works. The classifier in this case are four. The four classifiers used are K-nearest Neighbor, Kernel SVM, Decision tree and Random forest classifier.

The steps involved in the implementation involves:

Splitting of dataset: The dataset is divided into testing and training set. 75% of the dataset is considered for training and 25% for testing.

Preprocessing: This step involves filling or removal of the missing fields and getting a dataset that is clean.

Feature scaling: Feature scaling is also a part of preprocessing. It is a process in which the independent variables in the dataset are normalized within a fixed range so that no feature dominates the other for the prediction.

Feature extraction: Values of the features are extracted using some of the python modules. IP address, length of the URL, domain name, subdomains are some of the features being considered. These values are extracted and stored in a list.

IV. EXPERIMENTAL ANALYSIS AND RESULT

Among the four algorithms considered i.e. K-nearest neighbor, kernel support vector machine, decision tree and random forest classifier, the performance was evaluated using four factors.

The accuracy, recall score, precision and the F1 score of all the four algorithms were calculated. The equations to calculate the above mentioned are as follows:

Accuracy:

$$\text{Accuracy} = \frac{\text{TP} + \text{TN}}{\text{TP} + \text{TN} + \text{FP} + \text{FN}}$$

Fraction predicted correctly

Recall score:

$$\text{Recall (Sensitivity)} = \frac{\text{TP}}{\text{TP} + \text{FN}}$$

Fraction of positives predicted correctly

Precision:

$$\text{Precision} = \frac{\text{TP}}{\text{TP} + \text{FP}}$$

Fraction of predicted positives that are actually positive

F1 score:

$$F1 = \frac{2}{\frac{1}{\text{precision}} + \frac{1}{\text{recall}}} = \frac{2 * (\text{precision} * \text{recall})}{\text{precision} + \text{recall}}$$

The comparative plots of the above four performance metrics is as follows:

Accuracy:

Fig: 4.1. Comparative plot of accuracy score

The fig 4.1 shows that Random forest classifier has the highest accuracy compared to the other three models for the considered dataset.

Recall score:

Fig: 4.2. Comparative plot of recall score

The fig 4.2 shows that RFC again has a recall score of 98.28% which is high compared to the other three.

Precision: The fig 4.3 shows that precision score of Random forest classifier is the highest of all four and gives a precision score of 96%.

Fig: 4.3. Comparative plot of precision score

F1 score:

Fig 4.4. Comparative plot of F1 score

The fig 4.4 shows the comparative plot of F1 scores of the four algorithms and RFC again has the highest F1 score.

To brief the result, the Table 4.1 briefs of the scores of the four algorithms for the four-performance metrics.

Algorithm/ Metrics	Accuracy	Recall score	Precision	F1 score
KNN	94.72	96.5	94.02	95.24
Kernel SVM	96.49	97.89	95.8	96.83
Decision tree	93.7	95.11	93.51	94.31
Random Forest	96.82	98.28	96.0	97.13

Table 4.1: Performance metrics value of the algorithms

From the above table, it is clear that Random forest classifier is the best among the four classifiers considered and for the dataset chosen.

V. CONCLUSION

The exhibition of phishing is transforming into a propelled risk to this rapidly growing universe of development. The paper means to investigate this area by indicating a use case of recognizing phishing sites utilizing ML. It planned to fabricate a phishing detection method utilizing ML devices and strategies. The proposed system made use of four models of classification namely KNN, kernel SVM, decision tree and random forest classifier. Random forest classifier being an ensemble classifier gave the best accuracy score of 96.82% for the chosen dataset that considers about 30 features for the prediction.

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